

THE CONCEPT AND HISTORY OF BIBLIOTHERAPY IN PSYCHOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18814927>

Abstract: This research discusses the theoretical foundations of bibliotherapy in psychology, its historical stages of development, and its practical applications. It also substantiates the theory behind psychological research aimed at increasing the effectiveness of bibliotherapy within psychological mechanisms. The study scientifically analyzes data on individual and group forms of bibliotherapy, the specific aspects of working with children, adolescents, adults, and the elderly, as well as its role in the education system and clinical practice. Based on the research results, bibliotherapy proves to be an effective psychological tool for enhancing an individual's emotional stability, self-awareness, and socio-psychological adaptability.

Keywords: Bibliotherapy, psychological research, group bibliotherapy, mental health, reflection, empathy, psychological development.

ПОНЯТИЕ И ИСТОРИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ БИБЛИОТЕРАПИИ В ПСИХОЛОГИИ

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются теоретические основы, этапы исторического становления и направления практического применения библиотерапии в психологии. Также теоретически обосновывается эффективность библиотерапии как инструмента воздействия на психологические механизмы. В исследовании с научной точки зрения анализируются данные об индивидуальных и групповых формах библиотерапии, особенностях работы с детьми, подростками, взрослыми и пожилыми людьми, а также её роль в системе образования и клинической практике. Результаты исследования показывают, что библиотерапия является эффективным психологическим инструментом для повышения эмоциональной устойчивости личности, развития самосознания и улучшения социально-психологической адаптации.

Ключевые слова: Библиотерапия, психологические исследования, групповая библиотерапия, психическое здоровье, рефлексия, эмпатия, психологическое развитие.

PSIXOLOGIYADA BIBLIOTERAPIYA TUSHUNCHASI VA KELIB CHIQISH TARIXI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda psixologiyada biblioterapiya tushunchasining nazariy asoslari, tarixiy shakllanish bosqichlari va amaliy qo'llanish yo'nalishlari haqidagi asosiy ma'lumotlar muhokama qiliadi. Shuningdek, psixologik mexanizmlarda biblioterapiyaning samaradorlik omillari oshirish bo'yicha psixologik tadqiqotlarning nazariyasi asoslab berildi. Tadqiqotda biblioterapiyaning individual va guruh shakllari, bolalar, o'smirlar, kattalar hamda keksalar bilan ishlashdagi o'ziga xos jihatlari, ta'lim tizimi va klinik amaliyotdagi o'rni ilmiy jihatdan ma'lumotlar tahlil qilib o'tilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga asoslanganimizda biblioterapiya

shaxsning emotsional barqarorligi, o'zini anglash jarayoni va ijtimoiy-psixologik moslashuvchanligini oshirishda samarali psixologik vosita ekaninamoyon qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Biblioterapiya, psixologik tadqiqotlar, guruh biblioterapiyasi, ruhiy salomatlik, refleksiya, empatiya, psixologik rivojlanish.

INTRODUCTION

In psychology, the concept of bibliotherapy is interpreted as a psychotherapeutic approach based on the purposeful use of fiction, scientific, or journalistic literature in the process of improving a person's mental life, psychological development, and restoring emotional balance. At the center of this direction is the process of dynamic, meaningful, internal dialogue between the text and the reader. Bibliotherapy creates a psychological bridge between a person's inner experiences, conflicts, fears and hopes, identification processes, values, and social experience with images, plots, and ideas in the text. As a result, the reader has the opportunity to indirectly, safely, and symbolically review, understand, and transform their problem. The term bibliotherapy comes from the Greek words "biblion" - book and "therapeia" - treatment, which literally means "treatment with books." However, this approach is not limited to reading books; it combines the reading process with methods such as psychological analysis, reflection, discussion, written thinking, role identification, and emotional processing. The introduction of the term bibliotherapy into scientific circulation dates back to the beginning of the 20th century. During the First World War, wounded soldiers in military hospitals were given books and assisted in their mental recovery. In 1916, the American priest and essayist Samuel McChord Crothers published an article on bibliotherapy in *The Atlantic Monthly*, introducing this concept to the scientific community. After this, interest in bibliotherapy grew among librarians, psychiatrists, and psychologists in the USA and Europe. In the 1920s and 1930s, hospital libraries began compiling a list of literature specifically recommended for patients. With the development of clinical psychology and psychotherapy in the 1940s and 1950s, bibliotherapy also took on a more systematic form. Representatives of the psychoanalytic school saw the artistic text as a field that reveals unconscious processes. Sigmund Freud and his followers interpreted literary images in connection with a person's internal conflicts, suppressed desires, and childhood experiences. In the psychoanalytic approach, bibliotherapy allows the reader to recognize and process their unconscious impulses through identification with the character in the text. The events experienced by the hero resonate with the reader's inner conflicts, softening the defense mechanisms and accelerating the process of inner understanding. The development of humanistic psychology brought new meaning to bibliotherapy. Based on the principles of unconditional acceptance, empathy, and authenticity put forward by Carl Rogers, the learning process was viewed as a means of personal development. In bibliotherapy, the therapist or counselor does not give the reader a ready-made interpretation, but rather supports their personal communication with the text. The individual reviews their life experience through the text, forming a new system of meaning and values. Bibliotherapy can be carried out individually and in groups. In the individual form, the therapist selects a text that corresponds to the age, intellectual level, nature of the problem, and interests of the client. In group bibliotherapy, participants read the same work and share their thoughts and feelings. Group dynamics creates an additional therapeutic effect - an atmosphere of mutual support and empathy. Bibliotherapy plays a special role in working with children and adolescents. Through fairy tales, stories, and metaphorical texts, the child

symbolically perceives their fear, jealousy, anger, or feeling of loneliness. For example, the plot about the courage of a cowardly hero serves as an internal model for the child. In adolescence, works on the crisis of identity, relationships with peers, independence, and self-awareness can serve as a psychological support. Therefore, bibliotherapy requires a scientific basis, ethical principles, and an individual approach. In the modern era, digital technologies have given rise to new forms of bibliotherapy. Electronic books, audiobooks, online learning clubs, and psychological blogs are reaching a wide audience. This process democratizes bibliotherapy, but also increases the risk of uncontrolled and low-quality content. Therefore, it is important to select scientifically based literature recommended by specialists. Among the advantages of bibliotherapy are its economic efficiency, wide applicability, implementation at a psychological pace, and the development of internal independence. Restrictions are associated with reduced effectiveness in individuals with low reading literacy, severe psychotic states, or profound traumatic disorders. A deeper analysis of the methodological foundations of bibliotherapy contributes to a broader understanding of its theoretical and practical possibilities. First of all, in the process of bibliotherapy, the criteria for text selection are of great importance. The selected work should correspond to the age, cultural environment, intellectual potential, language competence, and the existing psychological problem of the individual. The identification mechanism may not work if the text is too complex or too distant from the person's experience. Conversely, excessively direct or didactic texts increase internal resistance. Therefore, in bibliotherapy, works with metaphorical, multilayered, symbolic, and open interpretations are considered more effective. The stages of the bibliotherapy process usually consist of four parts: preparation, reading, reflection, and integration. At the preparatory stage, the therapist or counselor identifies the problem with the client, sets the goal, and recommends relevant literature. At the reading stage, the individual studies the text independently or in a focused manner. At the stage of reflection, the process of inner understanding is activated through conversations, written reflection, or creative assignments on the content of the read material. At the integration stage, the acquired concepts are applied to real life, positive changes in behavior and thinking are consolidated. The types of literature used in bibliotherapy can be diverse. While literary works enhance emotional resonance and identification, popular science manuals provide psycho-educational information. Biographical works, on the other hand, have a motivational impact through real human experience. For example, life stories about people who have overcome difficulties strengthen hope and will in the reader. At the same time, poetry can also be an effective tool in bibliotherapy, since poetic language influences subconscious processes through short but deep emotional expression. Modern psychological research attempts to empirically study the effectiveness of bibliotherapy. Some scientific studies have shown that cognitive-bibliotherapy programs have shown positive results in individuals with mild and moderate depressive symptoms. In this case, the student learns to identify irrational schemes in their thoughts, reconstruct them, and form alternative methods of constructive thinking. At the same time, narrative texts intended for individuals who have experienced traumatic experiences can support the process of post-traumatic development. In the Uzbek cultural environment, there is a tradition of upbringing through proverbs, wise sayings, and epics. This tradition creates a natural foundation for bibliotherapy. For example, the use of examples of national literature on the themes of patience, perseverance, patriotism, or kindness strengthens the cultural identity of the individual and increases internal

stability. Bibliotherapy can also be widely used in the education system. School psychologists can carry out preventive work by recommending appropriate works in cases of students' adaptation problems, classroom conflicts, or low self-esteem. In higher educational institutions, literature covering topics related to professional identity, academic stress, and future plans serves as a spiritual support for young people. Within the framework of geropsychology, bibliotherapy is also important in working with the elderly. By reviewing life experiences, writing and reading memories, a person gives meaning to their life. This process can reduce the feeling of existential emptiness and loneliness. Reading familiar plots and poems, especially during the period of memory decline, helps maintain cognitive activity. The ethical aspects of bibliotherapy are also important. If the read text evokes a strong negative reaction in the person, this situation should be professionally processed. Maintaining the principles of confidentiality, empathy, and voluntariness increases the effectiveness of bibliotherapy. In recent years, interdisciplinary approaches related to bibliotherapy have also been developing. At the intersection of literary studies, linguistics, and psychology, the semantic and pragmatic layers of the text are studied. Neuropsychological studies show that areas related to empathy and imagination are activated in the brain during the learning process. These scientific results show that bibliotherapy has not only metaphorical, but also biological foundations. There are also forms of bibliotherapy, enriched with elements of creative writing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that bibliotherapy has been formed in the science of psychology as a scientifically based, historically rooted, and multifaceted direction of influencing a person's mental life through text. Bibliotherapy creates the possibility of processing the internal conflicts of the individual in a symbolic field, achieving emotional relaxation and a new understanding. In practice, bibliotherapy can be effectively used in mild to moderate psychological difficulties, stress, anxiety, low self-esteem, adaptation problems, and personal growth needs. In general, bibliotherapy retains its significance as a promising direction in strengthening the spiritual and emotional health of a person, integrating the power of words and meanings into the system of psychological assistance.

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